

Improving the electrochemical desalination performance of chloride-doped polyaniline activated carbon electrode by tuning the synthesis method

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Abstract

Activated carbon obtained from chloride-doped polyaniline (PAC/Cl) is an attractive material for brackish water desalination using capacitive deionization (CDI), due to its easy synthesis, low cost, and fast electrosorption kinetics. However, its low content of surface oxygen groups (SOGs) suppresses the salt adsorption capacity (SAC), despite high specific surface area. In this work, different strategies to improve the SAC and boost the kinetics of PAC/Cl electrodes were investigated by modifying the synthesis procedure. Firstly, the use of Pluronic™ F127 (PLR) as a template (CTAK electrode) allowed modification of the structure and textural properties of the carbonized and activated samples, increasing the SOG content by 26% (from 4.2 to 5.3 at.%), compared to the electrode prepared in the absence of PLR (CTAK*). Consequently, the electrode hydrophobicity was reduced by 2.1-fold (from 87.4 to 40.9°) and the desalination performance was enhanced, especially using an asymmetric electrode configuration (SAC enhancement from 11.4 to 21.0 mg g⁻¹). Despite the slower kinetics observed using CTAK, compared to CTAK*, when the SAC and electrosorption/desorption kinetics were considered together, CTAK outperformed CTAK* by ~2.0-fold (from 932 to 1560 mg g⁻¹ day⁻¹), in both symmetric and asymmetric configurations. As a second approach, the use of PLR combined with hydrothermal carbonization, despite leading to a 3D hierarchical framework, hindered the access to the pores, negatively impacting the process kinetics. The results showed that the use of PLR-modified PAC/Cl is a simple and effective strategy for obtaining low-cost activated carbons with distinct surface chemistry that can improve desalination performance.

Keywords: Capacitive deionization; Polyaniline activated carbon; Surface functional groups; Pluronic™ templating agent; Hydrothermal carbonization.

1. Introduction

The worldwide demand for fresh water is rising, as reported by the United Nations [1], requiring new resources to provide it, especially in semiarid regions. Consequently, technologies for the desalination of sea and brackish water are increasing in importance. Capacitive deionization (CDI) is a competitive technology for the desalination of brackish water, due to the lower energy required to remove ions [2,3]. Typically, a low potential (1.2 V) is applied to a pair of carbon electrodes, forcing the ions to move from the solution to the electrodes, where they are stored and form an electric double layer. This behavior, similar to that observed for supercapacitor technology, enables the desalination of water, while storing energy [4,5]. The CDI performance will depend on the textural properties of the carbon material (specific surface area, *SSA*, and pore size distribution, *PSD*), as well as its surface chemistry [6].

Activated carbons (ACs) obtained from carbonization and activation of polyaniline (PAni) doped with large anions have been reported as promising materials for CDI applications [7–9]. This is due to the high salt adsorption capacity (*SAC*) provided by their surface chemistry and textural properties [10]. In particular, for a membraneless process, the AC obtained from p-toluenesulfonic-doped polyaniline (PAC/PTS) displayed a remarkable *SAC* (22.2 mg g⁻¹) after synthesis optimization [11]. On the other hand, the AC derived from chloride-doped polyaniline (PAC/Cl) had poor desalination performance (*SAC* = 5.8 mg g⁻¹), despite having a significantly higher *SSA* (2652 m² g⁻¹) [10]. After a thorough investigation of the electrochemical properties and functional surface groups, assessed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis, it was found that the poor electrosorption capacity of PAC/Cl was mainly due to the low content of surface polar oxygen groups (SOGs). This evidenced that although high *SSA* is a desirable property for ACs used for CDI, the presence of SOGs, especially certain oxygen groups, is a critical feature for obtaining good desalination performance [10,12,13]. SOGs are expected to improve the electrosorption process, mainly due to increased hydrophilicity [14] and shift of the potential of zero-charge (E_{pzc}) of the electrode [15].

The desalination rate is also important in determining CDI performance. It has already been shown that ACs presenting fast adsorption/desorption kinetics can eventually remove more ions during a desalination cycle, compared to a material with high *SAC* [16,17]. An interesting observation was that PAC/Cl, despite low *SAC*, displayed uptake rates 27% faster than PAC/PTS at 1.2 V [10]. However, despite the slower kinetics, the *SAC* observed using PAC/PTS was 3.8 times higher than obtained using PAC/Cl. Hence, there is a challenge to be overcome, in order to make PAC/Cl technically feasible for application.

Another important aspect related to the choice of an AC for CDI is the production cost. In this regard, a disadvantage of PAC/PTS is the price and the large amount of p-toluenesulfonic acid used in

synthesis of the polymer. In contrast, HCl is less expensive, while lower amounts of this reagent are required to produce PAC/Cl, resulting in an AC that offers substantial cost benefits. The easy synthesis and low cost of PAC/Cl make it attractive for application in CDI, however, improvements in the *SAC* and kinetics are still a challenging issue for its effective use.

In this work we demonstrated for the first time that simply tuning the synthesis of PAC/Cl is a good strategy to produce a more competitive material in terms of *SAC*, kinetics, and cost, which would be suitable for electrochemical desalination. In this sense, the aim of this research was to understand how to improve the desalination performance of PAC/Cl by modifying the synthesis procedure. Accordingly, increase the number of surface functional groups and to develop a hierarchical pore structure looking for improvements of the *SAC* and the adsorption/desorption kinetics, respectively. The strategy used in this study was firstly to synthesize chloride-doped polyaniline, using HCl in the presence of the nonionic surfactant PluronicTM F127 (PLR). Pluronic triblock copolymers, such as P123 and F127, draw attention to the production of mesoporous carbon due to their commercial availability and tailorable morphologies [18–20]. This compound has been employed previously as a soft template, that act as pore-directing agent, due to the interest in the hydrogen/oxygen interactions that it is able to establish (a schematic illustration of the process is provided in Fig. S1) [20–22]. The strategy consists of filling the empty space of a template with a carbon source, followed by carbonization under an inert atmosphere and subsequent removal of the template [20]. The as-obtained polymer was then converted into activated carbon by two different carbonization procedures, either thermal or hydrothermal. Both treatments were followed by KOH activation, according to the optimized conditions determined in earlier work [10]. The thermal carbonization aimed at obtaining an AC with high SOGs content, while the hydrothermal carbonization was employed as a templating technique to achieve a hierarchical pore framework. The hypothesis adopted was that the introduction of these modifications in the synthesis methodology would enable the production of a competitive and suitable carbon for CDI applications.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

For the polyaniline synthesis, distilled aniline (99%, Sigma-Aldrich), hydrochloric acid (37%, J.T. Baker), ammonium persulfate (98%, Synth), and the nonionic surfactant PluronicTM F127 (12,600 g mol⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich) were used as monomer, doping anion source, oxidant, and templating agent, respectively. Potassium hydroxide (Sigma-Aldrich) was used as activating agent. For electrode

preparation, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, Sigma-Aldrich), n-methylpyrrolidone (NMP, 99.5%, Synth), and graphite sheet were used as binder, solvent, and current collector, respectively. Sodium chloride (Synth) was used in the desalination experiments. The commercial YP-80F activated carbon (Kuraray Co.) was used as the counter electrode and anode in the electrochemical characterization and desalination experiments (to provide asymmetry), respectively.

2.2 PAC/Cl synthesis and electrode preparation

Firstly, PANi was chemically synthesized using an adaptation of the procedure proposed by Xin et al. [20], shown schematically in Fig. S2. Briefly, 3 g of PLR was dissolved in 1 L of 0.1 M HCl, followed by addition of 55.3 mL of aniline (0.57 mol L^{-1} , previously distilled to prevent oxidation), under constant stirring. The solution was maintained at $3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [10,23] and the polymerization was started by slowly dripping 500 mL of the oxidant (2.2 mol L^{-1} $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$) into the monomer solution. A detailed mechanism of oxidative polymerization of aniline was described elsewhere [24,25]. The reaction was carried out for 11.5 h, under stirring. The chloride-doped PANi was filtered, washed with ethanol and deionized water, and dried in an oven at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 36 h. For comparison, the same synthesis was carried out in the absence of PLR.

The PANi/Cl samples were thermally carbonized in a tubular furnace (Lindberg Blue M, Thermo Scientific), using conditions similar to those described by Zornitta et al. [10], with heating at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h, under an atmosphere of N_2 (150 mL min^{-1}), but employing a slower heating rate ($1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$). For hydrothermal carbonization, the samples were firstly left for 20 h at $130 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (with heating at a rate of $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) (Xu et al. 2019) in a hermetically closed hydrothermal reactor (with a 100 mL Teflon liner), using 6 g of PANi/Cl in 60 mL of deionized water, under stirring (Fig. S2). After filtration and drying at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, the solid was thermally treated in the tubular furnace, following the same procedure described above for carbonization ($800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 2 h, $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$). The thermally carbonized samples were labeled as CT (using PLR) and CT* (without PLR), while the hydrothermally carbonized material was denoted HT. The asterisk indicates that the PANi/Cl synthesized in the absence of PLR was used for carbonization.

After carbonization, the samples were chemically activated with KOH in a proportion of 4:1 (KOH: PANi, w/w), followed by heating at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) for 1.5 h, under an atmosphere of N_2 (150 mL min^{-1}) [10]. The as-obtained activated carbons were washed with 0.5 mol L^{-1} HCl and warm water ($60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) until constant pH, followed by drying at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h (Fig. S3(a)). The activated CT and CT* samples were denoted as CTAK (with PLR) and CTAK* (without PLR), respectively, and the activated HT sample as HTAK. For comparison, a sample of HT was physically activated using CO_2 in the tubular furnace (150 mL min^{-1} CO_2 , $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, 2 h) [26]. This activated sample

was denoted HTAC. Finally, an additional sample was prepared by chemical activation of HTAC using KOH (850 °C, 10 °C min⁻¹, 1.5 h), which was labeled as HTACK (Fig. S3(b)).

All the electrodes were prepared by mixing 13 wt% of PVDF, previously dissolved in NMP, and 87 wt% of activated carbon. The slurry was spread onto a graphite sheet substrate using a doctor blade machine (Fig. S4). The carbon films were formed after evaporating the solvent in an oven at 80 °C for 12 h [16]. The thickness of the electroactive carbon film was 300-350 µm.

2.3 PAC/Cl and electrode characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were recorded from 5° to 70° (at 3° min⁻¹), using a Philips Analytical X'Pert-MPD X-ray diffractometer fitted with a Cu K α source ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images were acquired using a drop of aqueous suspension containing the sample deposited onto a carbon-coated copper grid and dried in air, followed by analysis using an FEI-TECNAI G2 F20 microscope operated at 200 kV. Elemental analysis (CHNS) was performed using a Flash 2000 CHNS/O Analyzer (Thermo Scientific) operated at 900 °C and calibrated with BBOT. The surface chemical groups were first identified by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy coupled with attenuated total reflection detection (ATR-FTIR), using a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrophotometer fitted with a diamond crystal cell. X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded using a laboratory spectrometer (SPECS GmbH, Berlin) with a monochromatic Al K α source ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$) at 50 W excitation. The X-rays were focused onto a 300 µm spot on the sample, using a μ -FOCUS 600 monochromator. Data were recorded with a PHOIBOS 150 NAP 1D-DLD analyzer, in fixed transmission mode. The energy step was set at 40 eV for survey scans and at 20 eV for high-resolution regions. The binding energy scale was calibrated using Au 4f_{7/2} (84.01 eV) and Ag 3d_{5/2} (368.20 eV). Charge compensation was required for data collection and the spectra were further calibrated against the C 1s internal reference. Data interpretation was performed with CasaXPS software. Shirley or two-point linear backgrounds were used, depending on the spectrum shape. Surface chemical analysis was performed based on the high-resolution spectra peak areas and CasaXPS sensitivity factors (where RSF of C 1s = 1.000). Raman spectra were recorded using a Horiba LabRAM HR Evolution spectrometer fitted with a Nd-YAG laser (532 nm; 600 x 50 grid). The degree of carbon ordering was estimated using the Raman peak intensity ratio (I_D/I_G), where the D mode indicates the presence of a disordered carbon structure, while the G mode is related to sp²-hybridized carbon atoms [27,28]. The textural properties of the activated carbons were assessed from N₂ adsorption/desorption, measured using an ASAP 2010 instrument (Micromeritics). Prior to the measurements, the samples were first degassed at 90 °C for 18 h and then at 200 °C for 6 h. The specific surface area was calculated using the Brunauer-Emmett-

Teller equation (SSA_{BET}), considering relative pressure (P/P_0) between 0.05 and 0.20 (linear region of the isotherm). The pore size distribution (PSD) and total pore volume (V_T) were calculated using the 2D-NLDFT heterogeneous surface model and SAIEUS software. The micropore (V_{mic}) and mesopore (V_{mes}) volumes were determined from the volume of N_2 adsorbed by pores ≤ 2 nm and by the difference between V_T and V_{mic} , respectively. The average pore diameter (d_{50}) was determined considering the pore diameter for which the volume adsorbed was half of V_T .

The electrode wettability (hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity) was assessed by measuring the contact angle, according to the sessile drop method, with a water droplet deposited onto the surface of the carbon electrode. After 10 s, the angle between the line tangential to the liquid interface of the drop and the baseline was measured.

The electrodes were electrochemically characterized by cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), using an electrochemical workstation (Multi Autolab/M204, Metrohm). A three-electrode Swagelok cell configuration was employed, with Ag/AgCl (KCl_{sat}) as the reference electrode, while AC from polyaniline and YP-80F (both 1 cm diameter) were used as the working (WE) and counter (CE) electrodes, respectively. The WE active mass varied from 1.3 to 1.5 mg. The CE mass was 3-fold higher than the WE. The voltammograms were recorded scanning the potential between -0.2 and 0.6 V vs. Ag/AgCl, at 5 mV s^{-1} , with 1.0 mol L^{-1} NaCl as the electrolyte solution. The specific capacitances (C_S) of the electrodes (F g^{-1}) were calculated using Eq. (1), where I is the current (A), v is the scan rate (V s^{-1}), and m is the mass of activated carbon in the working electrode (g).

$$C_S = \frac{I}{v m} \quad (1)$$

EIS measurements were performed at frequencies ranging from 1 mHz to 100 kHz, at 0.0 V vs. Ag/AgCl (0.2 V vs. SHE) and an alternating current amplitude of 10 mV. The ohmic (R_O) and charge-transfer (R_{CT}) resistances were estimated by fitting of the semicircle of the Nyquist plots using Metrohm Autolab NOVA v. 2.1 software. The potential of zero charge (E_{PZC}) was also determined by EIS in 0.01 mol L^{-1} NaCl (600 mg L^{-1}), applying 10 mHz (frequency), 30 mV (amplitude), and a potential step of 25 or 100 mV in a pre-established electrode potential range. The E_{PZC} of each sample was defined by the lowest capacitance value when normalized considering the lowest observed capacitance at each potential ($C/C_{min} = 1$). Consequently, it allows to know if the electrode has excess of positive or negative charges on the surface [11,29,30]. The capacitance at each potential was calculated using Eq. (2), where ω is the angular frequency and Z'' is the imaginary component of the impedance spectrum.

$$C_{EIS} = \frac{1}{|\omega Z''|} \quad (2)$$

2.4 Electrosorption experiments

The electrosorption experiments were performed in recirculating batch mode, using an electrochemical cell described previously [16]. Briefly, the cell was composed by two parallel electrodes (2.0 cm × 2.3 cm, mass of active material varying from 47.7 to 53.3 mg) contacting graphite current collectors attached to two acrylic plates. In order to avoid short circuit and allow electrolyte flow, the electrodes were separated by a plastic mesh. The cell was assembled using nuts and bolts, with rubber gaskets providing tight sealing (Fig. S5(a)).

The positive and negative electrodes were arranged in symmetric and asymmetric configurations. The asymmetry was established considering the relative position of E_{pzc} . For the desalination assays, a 25 mL volume of 0.01 mol L⁻¹ NaCl solution was recirculated through the CDI cell at a constant flow rate (26 mL min⁻¹), using a peristaltic pump (Masterflex L/S, Cole-Parmer) (Fig. S5(b)). A potentiostat (PGStat 204, Autolab) was used to apply 1.2 V and 0.0 V during the electrosorption and desorption steps, respectively. The desalination was carried out over 20 electrosorption/desorption cycles, in order to ensure the steady-state condition. Conductivity, pH, and temperature were continuously monitored in the outlet of the cell (Seven Excellence instrument, Mettler-Toledo). The conductivity value was corrected considering the pH and temperature fluctuations during the experiment, according to the methodology described by Lee et al. [31].

Salt adsorption capacity (SAC), charge efficiency (Q_E), and specific energy consumption (η), calculated using Eqs. (3), (4), and (5), respectively, were used as the metrics to evaluate the desalination performance of the electrode. In these equations, C_0 is the initial salt concentration (mg L⁻¹), C_t is the salt concentration (mg L⁻¹) at time t (s), V is the electrolyte volume (L), m_E is the total mass of the active material in both electrodes (g), z is the ion valence, F is the Faraday constant (96,485 A s mol⁻¹), I is the current (A), M_{NaCl} is the molecular weight of NaCl (58,400 mg mol⁻¹), E_{cell} is the cell potential in the electrosorption step (V), and m_{rem} is the mass of ions removed from the solution (mg).

$$SAC = \frac{(C_0 - C_t) \cdot V}{m_E} \quad (3)$$

$$Q_E = 100 \frac{z \cdot F \cdot V \cdot (C_0 - C_t)}{M_{NaCl} \int I dt} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = \frac{E_{cell} \int I dt}{m_{rem}} \quad (5)$$

The overall performance of the electrodes in the different configurations was evaluated according to the optimized salt removal (OSR) approach, proposed by Zornitta and Ruotolo [17], for simultaneous analysis of the electrosorption capacity and the adsorption/desorption kinetics. The OSR value (mg g⁻¹

¹ day⁻¹) is the amount of salt removed per gram of electrode material in a specified operational time (t_{op}). In brief, the electrosorption (k_e) and desorption (k_d) rate constants were fitted according to a pseudo first-order model (Eqs. (6) and (7), respectively), where $mSAC$ is the maximum value of SAC . The optimized electrosorption time (t_e) was evaluated by deriving the amount of salt removed, m_{sr} (Eq. (8)), and making it equal to zero. The desorption time (t_d) was calculated considering 99% of the electrode regeneration. The OSR value were calculated by replacing t_e in Eq. (8). This analysis is crucial for electrode evaluation, due to the influence on water productivity, since the electrosorption and desorption times affect the number of cycles performed.

$$SAC' = mSAC - SAC(t) = mSAC \cdot \exp(-k_e \cdot t_e) \quad (6)$$

$$SDC' = mSAC - SDC(t) = mSAC \cdot \exp(-k_d \cdot t_d) \quad (7)$$

$$m_{sr} = \frac{t_{op} \cdot m_E \cdot mSAC}{t_e + t_d} [1 - \exp(-k_e \cdot t_e)] \quad (8)$$

3. Results and discussion

The polymerization yields (Y_{PAni}) in the presence and absence of PLR were very similar (1.1 and 1.2 g PAni/mL aniline, respectively), indicating that PLR only acted as a templating agent and was not incorporated into the polymer. After hydrothermal carbonization, the yield decreased to 0.71 g char/g PAni, due to the release of volatile compounds, which increased when the thermal treatment was applied, leading to a lower yield (Y_{TC}) of 0.58 g char/g PAni. In the case of the thermally treated samples (CTAK* and CTAK), the Y_{TC} values were very similar (0.50 and 0.48, respectively), reinforcing that the template had not been incorporated into the precursor. The activation yield (g AC/g char) was calculated after physical activation using CO₂ (Y_{Ph}) or chemical activation with KOH (Y_{Ch}). The yields (Table S1) indicated a marked difference in the chemical reactions involved in these two activation processes, since Y_{Ch} was approximately 60% lower than Y_{Ph} . The lower release of volatile compounds during physical activation was expected to have a strong impact on SSA and pore formation, which was further evaluated using the N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms. The decrease in the volatile content during carbonization affects the porosity development, increasing fixed carbon content, and decreasing H/C and O/C ratios. On the other hand, during the activation step, the fixed carbon is consumed (Eq. 11), widening the pores [32,33], and releasing volatile compounds due to the reaction between the carbonized precursor and KOH, forming large cavities [11]. Another noteworthy feature was an increase of Y_{Ch} when PLR was used in the polymer synthesis (from 0.16 to 0.37 g AC/g char, for CTAK* and CTAK, respectively). As mentioned previously, the PLR was practically not incorporated into the polymer, so this trend was an indication that PLR changed the

PAni structure and the textural properties of the carbonized samples. Changing in the pore morphology by adding F127 during the N-doped mesoporous carbons preparation was also reported by Xin et al. [20]. These modifications seemed to hinder the access of the activating agent into the pores, decreasing the reactivity of the carbon.

In summary, the polymerization, carbonization, and especially activation significantly influenced the overall yields (Y_O , Table S1), expressed in g of AC produced per g of PAni. The highest Y_O (0.38 g AC/g PAni) was observed for the physically activated sample (HTAC), while the lowest value was observed for CTAK* (0.08 g AC/g PAni). The other chemically activated samples displayed Y_O values varying from 0.14 to 0.18 g AC/g PAni, which were higher than the values observed using the precursor synthesized in the absence of PLR (CTAK*). There was also an influence of the carbonization heating rate on Y_O , reaching 0.08 g AC/g PAni in this work, while Zornitta et al. [10] obtained 0.16 g AC/g PAni for PAC/Cl in the absence of PLR, applying a heating rate ($10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) 10-fold higher than employed in the present work.

3.1 AC characterization

Structural characterizations

PLR has been used in previous studies to template different materials, such as carbon molecular sieves [34,35]. The hypothesis adopted here was that by introducing PLR into the synthesis process, it would be possible to induce more organized mesoporous structures using hydrothermal syntheses. Nevertheless, the success of this approach was not evident from the results. The HRTEM micrograph (Fig. 1(a)) showed that the HT sample presented a three-dimensional hierarchical pore network, with a graphitic pattern ($I_D/I_G = 0.999$), as indicated by the Raman spectrum (Fig. 1(d)). This structure was maintained even after CO_2 activation (HTAC), although becoming a more organized structure with mesopores (Fig. 1(b)). Considering that $I_D/I_G(\text{HT}) > I_D/I_G(\text{HTAC})$, the structure became more organized after physical activation, in agreement with the HRTEM images (Figs. 1(a) and 1(b)). It should also be considered that the lower CO_2 reactivity, despite promoting the high Y_O observed for HTAC, might not promote the occurrence of oxygen groups on the edges of the graphitic basal planes, so a decrease of wettability would be observed. On the other hand, the chemical activations were associated with higher reactivity with carbon, which should lead to a material with a greater quantity of surface functional groups. In this case, lower activation yields and graphitization degrees (for example, $I_D/I_G(\text{HTAK}) > I_D/I_G(\text{HTAC})$) were detected.

Fig. 1. HRTEM images of HT (a), HTAC (b), and HTACK (c); (d) Raman spectra of the samples.

As an attempt to introduce more oxygen groups and make the HTAC electrode more hydrophilic, a further activation with KOH was performed, obtaining the HTACK material. As expected, the graphitization degree decreased for HTACK ($I_D/I_G = 1.022$, Fig. 1(d)), since the chemical activation enhanced the content of non-graphitic carbon (D band), probably due to the introduction of surface oxygen groups on the edges of graphitic basal planes. This trend became more evident for HTAK ($I_D/I_G = 1.063$). Regarding the pore structure, the HRTEM image of HTACK (Fig. 1(c)) revealed that the organized structure of HTAC was lost after its chemical activation, with HTACK presenting a 3D structure similar to that of HT, while high mesoporosity was preserved.

The contact angle analyses (Fig. 2(a)) revealed that the chemical treatment resulted in the hydrothermally treated carbons presenting a lower contact angle, due to the increased SOG content (discussed below). Hence, the HTACK electrode became more hydrophilic ($\theta = 76^\circ$) than HTAC (θ

= 102°), while the difference became even more substantial for HTAK ($\theta = 47^\circ$). This trend is explained by the increase of the surface interactions with hydroxyl groups and the decrease of the interactions with methyl groups [36], along with the improvement of surface area of the char, by reducing the porosity concentration towards the center of particles during carbonization [37]. This higher wettability was expected to improve the desalination performance, which was subsequently confirmed (discussed below).

Fig. 2. (a) Contact angles of the HTAC, CTAK*, and CTAK electrodes measured by sessile drop method after 10 s; (b) XRD patterns of the carbonized samples; (c) FTIR spectra, comparing CTAK and HTAK.

XRD analyses were performed to obtain additional insights about the activated carbon structure. In previous work using polyaniline activated carbons, it was demonstrated that a turbostratic carbon structure (Fig. S6(a)), composed of microcrystalline carbon fragments, was formed at low carbonization temperature (500°C). This structure provides an open framework with surface groups at the edges of the graphite basal planes, which improved the reactivity during the activation step, when compared with graphitic carbon [11]. In the present work, the XRD patterns of the HT, CT, and CT* samples (Fig. 2(b)) showed no evidence of turbostratic carbon ($2\theta = 20.7^\circ$), as expected, since all the samples were carbonized at 800°C . For these samples, broad diffraction bands at 24.5° and

44.4° were found, assigned to graphitic structures. It should be noted that after activation, the samples became less crystalline (Fig. S6(b)), with the exception of HTAC, for which the XRD pattern was the same as after carbonization (HT). This behavior was further evidence of low CO₂ reactivity leading to lower SOGs content, based on the high hydrophobicity of this material (Fig. 2(c)).

FTIR analysis was performed to obtain information about the surface groups present. Fig. 2(c) shows a comparison of the spectra for HTAK and CTAK, where broad bands in the regions 673-1396 cm⁻¹ (HTAK) and 690-1404 cm⁻¹ (CTAK) were observed, related to surface oxygen groups [38]. These bands are usually attributed to C-O stretching in ether or carboxylic groups, C-OH stretching in alcohols or phenolic groups (only phenolics in CTAK), carbonates, carboxyl-carbonates, and C=O stretching in carboxylic acids, lactones, or carboxylic anhydrides. These bands may also be attributed to the overlapped signatures of C-C stretching and twisting [39–41], as well as to C-H bonds of aromatic and heteroatomic species [42,43]. In addition, a broad band in the region 1396-1655 cm⁻¹ corresponded to the overlapped signatures of C-C bonding in the aromatic ring [43], C=C stretching of the benzenoid and quinoid rings [44], conjugated C=C stretching in olefinic species (C=C-O) [45], keto-enol groups, carbonates, carboxyl-carbonates, and stretching of carbonyl groups [38]. Carbonyl groups such as carboxylic acids, lactones, or carboxylic anhydrides were present in both materials, associated with C=O stretching at 1655-1971 cm⁻¹ [38]. A band at 2366-2590 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of phenolic groups and carboxylic acids, associated with C-OH and C=O stretching, respectively [38]. A band at 2561-2920 cm⁻¹ was related to C-H stretching, C-OH stretching in phenolic groups, C=O stretching in carboxylic acids, and CH₃-O group vibration [46]. A weak band at 3117-3232 cm⁻¹, which was only detected in the CTAK spectrum, was attributed to stretching of C-OH in alcohols or phenolic groups, C=O stretching in carboxylic acids, or adsorbed water [47]. HTAC presented a similar spectrum (Fig. S7), with an additional band at 2471-2851 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the C-H stretching vibration mode. These results were a good indication that activation promoted the formation of SOGs, which were expected to improve the electrochemical properties of the electrodes and their desalination performance.

The bulk and surface (< 5 nm) elemental compositions of the ACs, determined by elemental microanalysis and quantitative XPS, are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. All the PAC/Cl samples were mainly composed of carbon and oxygen, with a negligible content of nitrogen in the bulk material. The XPS survey spectra (Fig. S8) revealed the presence of only carbon and oxygen surface groups. Nitrogen surface groups were not detected, indicating that the N content from polyaniline was released during the chemical activation at high temperature [10]. According to our previous results [10], practically all chloride is released after carbonization and activation with KOH, as confirmed by XPS analysis (Fig. S8).

Table 1. CHNS elemental analysis of the activated carbons.

Material	Elemental composition (at.%)				
	C	H	N	S	O
CTAK*	93.0	1.1	0.8	0	5.1
CTAK	86.9	3.9	0.3	0	8.9
HTAK	91.1	0.3	0.7	0	7.9
HTACK	93.4	0.3	0.5	0	5.8

Fig. 3 shows the deconvoluted XPS core-level O 1s spectra, where the presence of carbonyl (C=O) groups (531.0 eV [48,49]) can be seen for all the samples, especially HTACK (39.6 at.%, Table 2). The band at 533.0 eV corresponds to the overlapped signatures for alcohol/ether (C-O), phenolic (C-OH), ether (C-O-C), carbonyl (C=O), and carboxyl (O-C=O) groups. The binding energy at 536.0 eV could be attributed to carboxylic (O-C-OH) groups [50], where CTAK and HTACK presented the highest (26.2 at.%) and lowest (13.5 at.%) contents, respectively. Compared to CTAK*, CTAK had 1.9-fold less carbonyl groups and 1.5-fold more carboxylic groups. Although carbonyl groups are reported to be electrochemically inactive, they can shift the E_{pzc} [51]. Acid groups, such as phenolic and carboxylic, give the material its polar character, making the electrode hydrophilic [52]. The same trend was observed from analysis of the C 1s XPS spectra (Fig. S9). The peaks were centered at 284.6 eV (C-H / C-C aromatic [53]), 286.3-287.1 eV (C=O [54] / C-O [55] / C-OH / C-O-C [49]), 289.3-290.4 eV ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions [56] / O-C-OH [10] / O-C=O [49]), and 292.0-294.7 eV (K $2p_{3/2}/2p_{1/2}$ spin-orbit pair [10], indicating traces of potassium from the chemical activation process). According to the XPS analysis (Table 2), the SOGs content varied from 4.2 to 5.7 at.%. The use of PLR increased the SOGs content in CTAK by 26%, compared to CTAK*, which would be expected to influence the carbon wettability, E_{pzc} , and, consequently, the electrosorption performance.

Fig. 3. Deconvoluted high resolution XPS O 1s spectra of CTAK* (a), CTAK (b), HTAK (c), and HTACK (d).

Table 2. Elemental composition of the near-surface region, obtained from XPS survey spectra, and surface groups determined from the deconvoluted high resolution XPS C 1s and O 1s spectra.

	Material	CTAK*	CTAK	HTAK	HTACK
Surface elemental composition (at.%)	C 1s	95.8	94.7	94.3	94.5
	O 1s	4.2	5.3	5.7	5.5
C 1s surface groups (at.%)	O-C-OH / O-C=O	18.0	19.4	16.3	18.8
	C=O / C-O / C-OH / C-O-C	14.7	14.2	16.8	14.4
	C-H / C-C _{arom}	66.0	65.8	66.0	62.0
O 1s surface groups (at.%)	O-C-OH	17.2	26.2	17.6	13.5
	C-O / C-OH / C-O-C / O-C=O	64.1	63.9	56.7	46.9
	C=O	18.7	9.9	25.7	39.6

In order to understand the influence of PLR on the textural properties of the samples, *SSA* and *PSD* were determined from the N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms (Fig. S10(a)). The type I isotherms indicated that the ACs were predominantly microporous (< 2 nm), while the type II isotherms with H4-type hysteresis loop could be attributed to mesoporosity (pore width > 2 nm), according to the IUPAC classification [57]. The textural parameters of the samples, calculated from the isotherms, are summarized in Table 3, together with the textural properties of the YP-80F used in asymmetric configurations. The data revealed that the use of PLR promoted a decrease of the mesoporosity from 57.2% (CTAK*) to 43.1% (CTAK), leading to a more microporous carbon, consequently enhancing *SSA_{BET}* by 10%. The isotherms also showed that the volume adsorbed by the physically activated sample (HTAC) increased significantly after the chemical activation with KOH (HTACK), indicating

further development of the electrode porosity. The *SSA* varied from 489 m² g⁻¹ for the CO₂-activated sample to 3148 m² g⁻¹ for HTACK. A large increase (6.4-fold) in the *SSA* of the HTAC material was achieved after chemical activation with KOH (HTACK), while the high mesoporosity was preserved (45.3 %*V_{mes}*, Table 3), corroborating the HRTEM results.

Table 3. Textural analysis of the electrodes, obtained from the N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms.

Material	<i>SSA_{BET}</i> (m ² g ⁻¹)	<i>V_T</i> (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	<i>V_{mic}</i> (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	<i>V_{mes}</i> (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	% <i>V_{mes}</i>	<i>d₅₀</i> (nm)
CTAK*	2756	1.71	0.73	0.98	57.2	2.2
CTAK	3035	1.70	0.97	0.73	43.1	1.8
HTAC	489	0.38	0.21	0.17	44.7	1.1
HTAK	1862	1.14	0.54	0.60	52.8	2.1
HTACK	3148	1.79	0.98	0.81	45.3	1.9
YP-80F [58]	2591	1.19	0.81	0.38	31.8	1.58

Notes: Specific surface area (*SSA_{BET}*); total pore (*V_T*), micropore (*V_{mic}*), and mesopore (*V_{mes}*) volumes; percentage of mesopores (%*V_{mes}*); average pore diameter (*d₅₀*).

The type of activation employed is related to the development of pores and *SSA*. Physical activation using CO₂ generates a more mesoporous structure, formed from the fast reaction between carbon and CO₂ at high temperatures, based on the Boudouard equilibrium (Eq. 9), in which the CO_(g) produced is responsible for the pore enlargement [59–61]. On the other hand, the chemical activation using KOH leads to a large loss of volatiles, producing microporous activated carbons with higher *SSA* and pore volume [11,12]. According to Eq. 10, the carbon oxidizes to form carbonates and metallic potassium. The porosity is developed during activation due to the mobility of the metallic K within the structure, enlarging the pores, and the reaction between potassium carbonate and the carbon (Eq. 11), increasing the carbon burn off [62]. Concomitantly, the production of larger SOG content is expected [26], impacting the carbon hydrophilicity.

Comparing CTAK and HTACK, the SSA increased by only 3.7% when physical and chemical activation were combined, while similar $\%V_{mes}$ and d_{50} were obtained. The SSA values for the carbonized samples, CT and HT, were very low (24 and 65 $m^2 g^{-1}$, respectively), confirming that activation was essential for obtaining carbons suitable for CDI. The PSD (Fig. S10(b)) confirmed the presence of a large volume of mesopores, occupying between 43.1 and 57.2% of the total pore volume.

Finally, it is worth noting that the PAC/Cl synthesized in the absence of PLR (CTAK*) in this work, despite presenting similar SSA , had a $\%V_{mes}$ 2.5-fold higher than obtained for the same material by Zornitta et al. [10] (2652 $m^2 g^{-1}$ SSA_{BET} and 23% V_{mes}). The increase of $\%V_{mes}$ obtained here could mainly be attributed to the slow carbonization heating rate used in this work (the other synthesis parameters were very similar).

Electrochemical characterizations

The electrochemical properties of the electrodes were characterized using an asymmetric configuration similar to the one subsequently tested in desalination experiments. The synthesized material was used as the working electrode, while the counter and reference electrodes were YP-80F carbon and Ag/AgCl, respectively. Fig. 4(a) shows the polarization curve in terms of charge storage capacity, for the different electrodes. The quasi-rectangular shape of the voltammograms indicates the capacitive and conductive behavior of the electrodes, typical of supercapacitors. Deviation from such behavior, with distortion of the rectangular shape, usually indicates a resistive component of one of the electrodes, which here suggested that CTAK was more conductive than CTAK*. Fig. 4(b) shows the Nyquist plots from which the ohmic (R_{Ω}) and charging resistances (R_{CT}) were determined by fitting the semicircle domain. The R_{Ω} value, attributed to the contact (current collector) and electrolyte resistances, were very similar ($\sim 0.4 \Omega$), as expected, since the same cell was used in all the experiments. The R_{CT} is an intrinsic property of the carbon electrode and was affected by the surface chemistry and polarization resistance of the electrodes. In this sense, the R_{CT} were 0.22, 0.18, 0.15, and 0.11 Ω for HTACK, CTAK*, CTAK, and HTAK, respectively. These values were similar and very low, when compared to other values reported in the literature, e.g. 0.46-1.05 Ω for PAC/PTS [16], 0.34 Ω for micro-meso-macroporous 3D graphene [63], and 0.83-36.7 Ω for polyglycerol activated carbon (PGAC) [6]. indicating that the electrodes could be easily charged. The CTAK* electrode presented a significant decrease in the R_{CT} (98.8%), compared to the same material reported by Zornitta et al. [10] (14.7 Ω), ascribed to the modification of the carbonization step, which impacts the AC structure, as previously discussed considering the Raman spectra.

Fig. 4. (a) Cyclic voltammograms of the electrodes (at 5 mV s^{-1}), and (b) Nyquist plots. Counter electrode: YP-80F. Electrolyte: $1.0 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaCl}$.

3.2 Desalination performance

The desalination performance was evaluated for both symmetric and asymmetric electrode configurations, in an attempt to improve the electrosorption rate by minimizing the effect of co-ion repulsion [64]. To this end, an analysis of E_{pzc} was performed to select the most suitable electrode configuration in the asymmetric CDI cell. The results (Fig. 5(a)) indicated that the most appropriate configuration was an asymmetric cell with YP-80F as positive electrode [65] and the synthesized electrodes as cathodes. The reason for this selection was the presence of negative surface charges provided by the SOGs on the synthesized active materials, as confirmed by the XPS analysis, and the more basic character (~ 4.5 -fold more basic than acidic groups) of YP-80F, as reported in the literature [66]. As an example of this effect, Fig. 5(a) shows how the high SOGs content (Table 2) shifted the E_{pzc} of the synthesized materials to higher values. In accordance with its lower SOGs content, CTAK* presented the lowest E_{pzc} (less negative surface charge) of the materials tested. It should also be noted that the HTAC electrode was not included in this analysis, despite its high mesoporosity (44.7%, Table 3) and organized structure (Fig. 1(b)), because its significant hydrophobic behavior ($\theta = 102.4^\circ$, Fig. 2(a)) meant that it was not considered a suitable candidate for use in the desalination experiments. This high contact angle could be attributed to the low SOGs content observed when physical activation was employed [26].

The results of the desalination experiments (Fig. 5(b)), comparing CTAK and CTAK*, clearly demonstrated the positive impact on CDI performance of using PLR during the synthesis process. As a result, the SAC increased substantially from 6.7 to 11.4 mg g^{-1} , using the symmetric configuration (Fig. 6(a)). Moreover, the use of an asymmetric CTAK|YP-80F configuration not only provided a

significant increment of SAC (from 11.4 mg g^{-1} to 21.0 mg g^{-1}), but also an increment of 24% for Q_E (Fig. 6(b)). This improvement confirmed the efficacy of this configuration for avoiding co-ion repulsion, consequently resulting in higher desalination capacity and lower specific energy consumption (29%, Fig. 6(c)). Additionally, the results were in agreement with the XPS analyses (a large quantity of SOGs shifted E_{pzc} to a more positive value, $0.2 \text{ V vs. Ag/AgCl}$) and the lower hydrophobicity of this material ($\theta = 40.9^\circ$, Fig. 2(a)). The presence of oxygen functional groups prevents the co-ion repulsion, improving the charging efficiency [11].

Fig. 5. (a) Electrode E_{pzc} values and (b) electrosorption profiles of the electrodes in symmetric and asymmetric configurations. Electrolyte: $600 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ NaCl}$; E_{cell} : 1.2 V (adsorption) and 0.0 V (desorption).

As a contrast with the performance of the material prepared in the absence of PRL (CTAK*), the use of an asymmetric configuration CTAK*|YP-80F did not improve the desalination performance (6.3 mg g^{-1}), keeping the charging efficiency at very low values (a moderate increase from 20 to 28%). This could be attributed to the lower E_{pzc} ($0.1 \text{ V vs. Ag/AgCl}$, Fig. 5(a)), which resulted not only from the lower negative surface charge content of CTAK*, but also the type of functionalities. According to the XPS results, CTAK* had 1.9-fold more carbonyl groups, compared to CTAK, directly affecting the E_{pzc} shift [51]. Additionally, these functionalities contributed to the lower hydrophilicity of CTAK* ($\theta = 87.4^\circ$) than CTACK ($\theta = 40.9^\circ$), leading to the lower electrosorption values obtained for the material prepared in the absence of PRL [52]. It could be concluded from these results that PLR strongly influenced the polyaniline synthesis, by modification of the activation process, producing ACs with distinct surface chemistry that promoted the electrosorption of ions.

Fig. 6. Desalination performance of the electrodes in symmetric and asymmetric configurations: (a) SAC , (b) Q_E , and (c) η .

In comparison with the activation methodologies, it was found that the hydrothermally synthesized electrodes (HTAK and HTACK) employed in the symmetric configuration did not present any significant improvement, in terms of SAC (9.0 and 12.5 mg g⁻¹, respectively), compared to the thermally activated electrode (CTAK, $SAC = 11.4$ mg g⁻¹). As shown in Fig. 6(a), use of the asymmetric configuration resulted in only slight increases of the SAC values (9.3 and 13.1 mg g⁻¹ for HTAK and HTACK, respectively), relative to the symmetric configuration, which were far lower than the value obtained for CTAK (21.0 mg g⁻¹). The lower SAC observed for HTAK, compared to CTAK, could be attributed to its lower SSA . In the case of HTACK, despite having higher SSA (Table 3) and similar SOGs content (Table 2), compared to CTAK, the low content of surface polar groups (phenolic and carboxylic) made the electrode less hydrophilic and limited increase of the SAC , even using the asymmetric configuration. In addition to this, the Q_E values were lower, irrespective of the cell configuration, leading to a higher energy demand, compared to the CTAK electrodes.

For evaluation of the kinetics of the processes, the electrosorption and desorption constants were calculated (Fig. S11), together with the OSR values (Table 4). The thermally activated carbons presented faster electrosorption kinetics, compared to the samples prepared using the hydrothermal method. For the CTAK electrode, a higher value of k_e was obtained for the symmetric configuration than for the asymmetric arrangement. This feature, which contrasted with the SAC values, could be ascribed to the lower $\%V_{mes}$ of YP-80F than CTAK (Table 3). The mesopores acted as large avenues for ion diffusion, with a high proportion of mesopores significantly influencing mass transfer.

Table 4. Kinetics and *OSR* performances of the electrodes in symmetric and asymmetric configurations.

Electrode configurations	Performance metrics					
	$k_e \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_d \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	t_e (s)	t_d (s)	N_{cycles}	<i>OSR</i> (mg g ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)
CTAK* symmetric	11.7	-	369	890	78	479
CTAK* asymmetric	8.57	16.5	194	279	183	932
CTAK symmetric	6.28	7.88	299	585	98	945
CTAK asymmetric	4.90	7.64	361	603	90	1560
HTAK symmetric	5.12	-	963	1398 [§]	47	378
HTAK asymmetric	3.19	4.97	525	926	60	450
HTACK symmetric	4.51	5.72	415	806	71	752
HTACK asymmetric	4.31	7.26	392	634	85	901

Notes: Electrosorption (k_e) and desorption (k_d) kinetic constants; optimized electrosorption time (t_e); desorption time (t_d); number of cycles ($N_{cycles} = t_{op.}(t_e + t_d)^{-1}$); and optimized salt removal (*OSR*). [§] time considering 99% desorption.

An interesting observation for the CTAK* electrode was that the *SAC* (6.7 mg g⁻¹) was similar to the value reported earlier [10] for PAC/Cl (5.8 mg g⁻¹, Table 5), even though a slower carbonization heating rate was used for CTAK*. However, the modification appeared to have a strong influence on increasing %*V_{mes}* for CTAK* (57.2%), compared to PAC/Cl (23%), resulting in a 3.5-fold enhancement of the electrosorption kinetics.

Contrary to the initial hypothesis, the HTAK and HTACK electrodes presented slower rates of electrosorption and desorption, compared to the thermally carbonized samples (CTAK), for both symmetric and asymmetric configurations (Table 4). This indicated that the use of PLR in combination with hydrothermal carbonization, despite leading to a three-dimensional hierarchical structure with similar textural properties in terms of %*V_{mes}* and *d*₅₀, did not positively affect the process kinetics. Furthermore, these results suggested that the 3D arrangement of the PLR-hydrothermally carbonized samples was probably the most important factor affecting pore tortuosity and the diffusion path into the micropores [67,68]. In summary, the combination of the values of *SAC*, k_e , and k_d resulted in the HTAK and HTACK electrodes presenting the worst performances in terms of *OSR*. This outcome evidenced that hydrothermal carbonization, besides being time-consuming and increasing the preparation cost, would not be recommended, since it did not bring any advantage in terms of desalination performance.

Overall, for CTAK, balancing the positive effect on *SAC* and negative effect on the kinetics, an outstanding *OSR* value of 1560 mg g⁻¹ day⁻¹ was obtained, which was even higher than obtained in

previous work using PAC/PTS (Table 5). Therefore, it could be considered that the main goal of this work was achieved by introducing PLR into the PANi synthesis, obtaining a cost-effective PAC electrode by replacing PTS⁻ with chloride as the doping anion during AC preparation. In comparison with other similar ACs reported in the literature (Table 5), the values obtained using CTAK in a membraneless cell revealed the excellent potential of this material for use in capacitive deionization.

Table 5. Comparison of different polyaniline activated carbons ($E_{cell} = 1.2$ V, 600 mg L⁻¹ NaCl).

Material	SSA_{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	Configuration	SAC (mg g ⁻¹)	$k_e \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	OSR (mg g ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	η (J mg ⁻¹)	Reference
CTAK*	2756	Symmetric	6.7	11.7	479	10.1	This work
CTAK	3035	Asymmetric	21.0	4.9	1560	2.4	This work
PAC/Cl	2652	Symmetric	5.8	3.3	-	6.9	[10]
PAC/PTS	3649	Symmetric	22.2	6.4	1517	4.2	[11]
PAC/PTS[§]	3444	Asymmetric	20.7	2.9	791	2.7	[58]
PAC/S[§]	2630	Asymmetric	16.4	3.1	683	3.4	[58]

Notes: PAC/Cl: AC from chloride-doped polyaniline; PAC/PTS: AC from p-toluenesulfonate-doped polyaniline; PAC/S: AC from sulfate-doped polyaniline. [§] NaCl concentration = 1080 mg L⁻¹.

Finally, a comparison of the CDI performance using the CTAK with other activated carbon electrodes is shown in Table S2. Although SAC varied from 3.5 to 27.1 mg g⁻¹, a superior OSR value was obtained in this work (1560 mg g⁻¹ day⁻¹), except for the value obtained by Choi and Yoon [69] (2072 mg g⁻¹ day⁻¹) using membrane CDI, but it is worth mentioning that the use of membrane imposes an additional cost.

4. Conclusions

In this work, it was demonstrated that tuning the synthesis of PAC/Cl is essential for improving CDI performance. Despite presenting similar SSA , a 10-fold reduction of the carbonization heating rate applied in the CTAK* synthesis (1 °C min⁻¹) led to a 2.5-fold increase in $\%V_{mes}$ (from 23.0 to 57.2 %), increasing the electrosorption kinetics 3.5-fold (from 3.3 x 10⁻³ to 11.7 x 10⁻³ s⁻¹), compared to PAC/Cl. However, CTAK* maintained low desalination performance, even in the asymmetric configuration (6.3 mg g⁻¹), which could be attributed to the lower SOGs content (4.2 at.%) that shifted E_{pzc} to lower values (0.1 vs Ag/AgCl), leading to less negative surface charge. On the other hand, the higher SOG content (5.3 at.%) and the increase of surface polar groups (phenolic and carboxylic groups) in CTAK, improved the electrode hydrophilicity (the contact angle dropped from 87.4 to

40.9°) and shifted E_{pzc} to more positive values (0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl), compared to CTAK*. These results confirmed the role of PLR in modifying the PANi structure, which altered the activation process with KOH, leading to higher SAC . Overall, the surface chemistry seemed to be the most important factor affecting desalination performance. Using the asymmetric configuration, SAC increased from 11.4 to 21.0 mg g⁻¹, which was similar to the value obtained using PAC/PTS (22.2 mg g⁻¹). At the same time, Q_E increased by 24%, mitigating the deleterious effect of co-ion repulsion, improving desalination performance and providing a 29% reduction in specific energy consumption. Although the low % V_{mes} of YP-80F (31.8%) limited the electrosorption/desorption kinetics of CTAK, a high OSR value (1560 mg g⁻¹ day⁻¹) was achieved, which was even higher than obtained using PAC/PTS (1517 mg g⁻¹ day⁻¹). The cost of producing 1 kg of PAC/Cl was estimated to be ~3-fold lower than the cost of producing the same quantity of PAC/PTS. Therefore, the findings of this work revealed the benefits of introducing PLR as a PANi template, in order to obtain a cost-effective activated carbon for application in CDI.

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